

EMPIRICAL EVALUATION OF CLINICAL SUPERVISION MODEL OF SUPERVISING PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract:

There are few empirical evidences of the effectiveness of the various teaching practice supervision models. This study is aimed to add to the dearth of empirical evidences of effectiveness of teaching practice supervision model by evaluating the clinical supervision model. Clinical supervision is a method of supervision whereby the supervisor is involved with the pre-service-teacher in a close, 'helping, relationship'. Essentially, clinical supervision in education involves a teacher trainee receiving information from a supervisor who has observed the teacher trainee's performance and who serves as both a mirror and a sounding board to enable the teacher trainee critically examine and possibly alter his/her own professional practice. Within the context of such supervision, ideas are shared and help is given in order to improve the teacher trainee's ability through the analysis of objective data that is collected during the observation.

Keywords: teaching practice, pre-service teacher, supervision, clinical model, evaluation of teaching

1. Introduction

The purpose of clinical supervision is to help pre-service teachers develop and improve through cooperative planning, observation, and feedback. Within the context of clinical supervision, ideas are shared and help is given in order to improve the pre-service teacher's ability through the analysis of objective data that is collected during the observation. Pre-service teacher trainees have negative expectations regarding supervision. They see it as adversarial and designed to only point out deficient areas in their teaching practice. The objective of this study is to examine supervisors' utilization

of the clinical supervision models in evaluating pre-service teachers on teaching practice exercise. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

1. To determine if supervisors create a rapport with pre-service teachers before the actual supervision of the teaching in the classroom;
2. To determine supervisors utilization of actual classroom observation strategy in evaluating teaching practice;
3. To determine supervisors utilization of the pre-observation conference strategy in evaluating teaching practice;
4. To determine the analysis of the feedback strategy in evaluating teaching practice.

The following research questions were then posited for the study:

- Do supervisors create rapport with pre-service teachers before the actual supervision of the teaching in the classroom?
- What is the extent of supervisors' utilization of actual classroom observation strategy in evaluating teaching practice?
- What is the extent of supervisors' utilization of the pre-observation conference strategy in evaluating teaching practice?
- To what extent do supervisors' utilize the feedback strategy in the supervision of teaching practice evaluation?

2. Perspective/theoretical framework

The quality of education provided in any society and the nature of the change affected by that education are both dependable on the quality of teachers and the effectiveness of their teachings in schools. In the professionalization of pre-service teachers, they are expected to have a practical experience of teaching during the course of their training referred to as teaching practice. Teaching practice is an exercise in which the pre-service-teacher is guided to acquire practical skills and competences necessary for effective teaching (Hamilton-Ekeke, 2012). This valuable experience and expertise are usually acquired by exposing pre-service-teachers to schools to experience real life classroom environment. They then get feedback from their peers, cooperating teachers and university supervisors in order to be more effective educators (Hamilton-Ekeke, 2016).

Gyuse (2006) stated that the majority of the people in the teaching profession in Nigeria are in the profession as a second or last choice. This is due to failure of being admitted into other programmes of their choice in the university. Mkpandioke (2006) observed that for the past 15 years, scholars have embarked on extensive research in order to adopt teaching techniques to tackle the issues of the differences among individual learners with regard to the social and institutional contexts of teaching and the evaluation of teaching practice. Many theories and models have been put forward by different scholars in the evaluation of this laudable programme (teaching practice). Some of them include but not limited to Clinical Supervision; Developmental

Supervision; Scientific Supervision; Accountable Supervision; Artistic Supervision; Self-assessment Supervision. The purpose of this study is to examine one of these numerous models of supervisions of pre-service-teachers and evaluate its effectiveness. The teaching practice model evaluated in this study is the clinical supervision model.

2.1 Clinical Supervision Model of Teaching Practice Evaluation

The term 'supervision' has been given different definitions but from an educational point of view; the definition implies supervision as a strategy that emphasizes on offering professional support for the improvement of instruction (Hamilton-Ekeke, 2015). Supervision is a complex process that involves working with teachers and other educators in a collegial, collaborative relationship to enhance the quality of teaching and learning within the schools and promotes the career development of teachers which in turn leads to improvement in teaching performance and greater student learning. Its' basic purpose is to enhance the educational experiences and learning of all students (Beck & Kosnik, 2000).

The idea of clinical supervision was first developed by Goldhammer (1969) in the 1960s as cited in Hopkins, Scott, Moore and Kenneth (1993). The basic idea of clinical supervision was to focus on data collection process during observations of the teaching. Cogan (1973) developed and supported clinical supervision and took particular attention to the importance of professional interactions between stakeholders (in this case, pre-service teacher and observer usually the assigned supervisor) to help pre-service teacher's professional development.

The term clinical supervision was adopted from the medical profession as it describes a process in which the skills and knowledge of trainees are developed in practice. For instance, apprentice surgeons learn their trade by first observing the skilled practitioner at work; then by undertaking surgery under close surveillance. In this way, they begin to develop their 'professional artistry' (Sullivan & Glanz, 2005), so is the practice of teaching.

Essentially, the clinical supervision model alters the roles of supervisor, co-operating teacher and pre-service teacher (teacher trainee) into more of a collegial relationship where the teacher trainee can use the supervisor and co-operating teacher (this is the teacher in the school where the pre-service teacher has being posted to do the teaching practice, the co-operating teacher is usually assigned to the pre-service teacher by the school) for both reflection and as a resource for improvement. Supervision is not the act of instructing pre-service teachers, but, rather the actions that enable pre-service teachers improve instruction (Gebhard, 1984). According to Acheson & Gall (2003), the ultimate goal of the supervisor is to improve pre-service teacher trainees' classroom instruction. Clinical supervision, therefore, allows for objective feedback, which if given in a timely manner, will lead to improved results. Clinical supervision helps to diagnose instructional problems and provides valuable information which can lead to solving such problems. As a result, pre-service teachers are able to clearly see differences in what they are doing in reality, and what they think they are doing. Where

necessary, improvements in instruction are highlighted and pre-service teacher, through clinical supervision, are able to develop new skills and strategies which will be replicated as needed. The Clinical Supervision Model cycle has four stages. Each is an indispensable part of the cycle. Although each of the stake holders is essential, the supervisor has the responsibility for the organization and successful implementation of the clinical supervision model – that is why this study concentrated on the supervisor.

Based on the clinical mode, the supervisor:

1. Should organize a meeting with the teacher trainee and co-operating teacher prior to teaching to provide a plan for future observations;
2. Should conduct a systematic and non-judgmental observation and data collection of the teacher trainee teaching;
3. Should spend time analyzing the data collected prior to the post teaching 3-way conference;
4. Should organize a meeting after the teaching to analyze the teacher trainee's teaching performance, provide supportive feedback and make plans for improvement for future teaching (Acheson & Gall, 1997).

During the teaching practice, the pre-service teachers are sent out from the University and College to primary, secondary, commercial, comprehensive and technical schools to teach for a period of time as a part of their training. According to Andabai (2011) during this practice a student is supervised and evaluated not only by a supervisor allotted to him but also by a group of other lecturers who supervises him as a team as well as a staff of the school in which he is teaching. Akpomi (2001) argued that the need for this different evaluation is to make sure that the pre-service teacher is properly corrected and graded.

3. Methods/mode of inquiry

The design of the study is a retrospective survey design. It is a study of an occurrence that has already taken place and is usually limited by recall. The sample for this study consisted of all the one hundred and forty (140) lecturers in the Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria who participated in the 2015/2016 teaching practice exercise which occur in the fall of 2016 (September to November). The research proposal was approved by the Institution Research Board and consent letters were distributed to lecturers, every lecturer indicated willingness to participate in the research. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire eliciting opinion on the use of clinical supervision stages to supervise pre-service teachers, see Appendix A attached. The questionnaire was a four point Likert scale developed by the researchers and evaluated for face and content validity by experts in measurement and evaluation department of the Faculty of Education. The reliability of the instrument was tested using test-re-test method and a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.84$ was realized using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to analyse the two sets of data

collected. The coefficient of $r = 0.84$ is within the acceptable benchmark of reliable coefficients.

3.1 Data sources

The data sources for this study were primary data generated from the questionnaire to answer the research questions posited for the study. The percentages of responses based on the frequency of response were presented on tables.

4. Results

The first stage of clinical supervision model which is the establishment of rapport with the pre-service teachers by the supervisor to help the pre-service teacher to relax and compose him/herself for the exercise was indicated as lacking. Supervisors usually do not inform pre-service teachers of when they are coming for the supervision. They are usually taken unawares. Most of the lecturers are not familiar with clinical supervision model of evaluation of teaching practice. Though some of the activities they do in their supervision can be categorized under some of the stages of the model which are pre-observation conference, actual classroom observation and feedback.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, Niger Delta University supervisors' awareness of clinical supervision model of evaluation of teaching practice is abysmal. They do not inform their supervisees (pre-service teachers) before visiting them in their teaching practice schools for supervision thereby taking them unawares. Examination usually is planned therefore supervisors should plan with pre-service teachers to make adequate arrangement, preparation for the visit and agree on a suitable time for classroom observation. This is recommended as teaching practical evaluation accounts toward the overall evaluation of a pre-service teacher's final grading.

5.1 Scholarly significance of the study

Teaching practice is the most vital part of pre-service teacher's career training; this is because it is during this practice that the pre-service teacher applies the methods and theories of education which he/she has learnt. The findings from this study imply that supervisor's not creating rapport with their supervisees before actual supervision could lead to poor performance as a result of nervousness. Creating rapport will help relax the nerves and assessment pressures on the pre-service teacher. Supervisors' utilization of feedback after the actual classroom observation strategy is very important as it ensures that the pre-service teachers are not humiliated and dehumanized, especially in the presence of their students or learners. Indication of supervisors' utilization of pre-observation conference strategy is really a helping process; as it serves as a period of refreshing what the pre-service teacher has learnt about teaching strategies, classroom

management, and selection of materials for proper impartation of knowledge to the learners before embarking on the teaching practice exercise. Appropriate feedback on a one-on-one will promote goodwill and build confidence in the pre-service teacher.

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Appendix I

Section (A)

Personal Data:

Gender: Male Female

Position/ Status: Professor Reader Senior Lecturer Lecturer 1

Lecturer II Assistant Lecturer

Working Experience: 0-5yrs 6-10yrs 11-15yrs 16yrs & above

Section (B)

Please tick (✓) the column considered most appropriate in your opinion.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD
Supervisors Establishment of Rapport with Student Teachers Strategy					
1	Supervisors analyze the lesson plan of the supervisee teacher before classroom visit.				
2	Supervisors are friendly with the student teachers before the actual supervision in the classroom				
3	Supervisors visit student teachers after informing them				
4	Supervisors plan and make agreements with teachers on the suitable time for classroom observation				
5	Supervisors discuss with teachers on the objective of the lesson before the actual presentation.				
Supervisors Utilization of Actual Classroom Observation Strategy					
6	Supervisors follow up the lesson of the student teacher attentively from the beginning to the end				
7	In the last teaching practice exercise, my Supervisor come to observe my teaching for more than two times				
8	Supervisors convince student teachers that classroom visit is a helping process in his/her teaching				
9	Supervisors sit at the back of the classroom while observing without interrupting on the acting teacher				
10	Supervisors record important data on the teaching learning process and how the student teacher is performing				
11	Supervisors organize a meeting with the teacher trainee prior to teaching to provide a plan for future observations, before sending them out to schools				
Supervisor's Utilization of the Pre-Observation Conference Strategy					
12	Supervisors uses the pre-observation conference strategy in a way of re-orientation				
13	Supervisor discusses issues related to teaching strategies, classroom management, selection of materials etc. to student teachers before sending them out to schools				
14	Supervisors discuss with the supervisee teacher on the collected data during the class observation for improvement				
15	Supervisors give immediate feedback to the teachers in the classroom while teaching is in progress				
16	Supervisors give comments for the supervisee teachers to read rather than discussing face- to- face.				

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Supervisor's Utilization of the Feedback Strategy				
17	Supervisors organize a meeting after my supervisee teaching to analyze his teaching performance, provide supportive feedback and make plans for improvement for future teaching			
18	Supervisor's comments and judgments where based on their notes taking on my performance in the class while he observe my teaching			
19	Supervisor takes at the grey areas and areas of success, before fashioning out a strategy to present a feedback to the student-teacher.			
20	Supervisors analyze the teachings of the student teachers without involving them			

Key:

SA: Strongly Agreed; A: Agreed; SD: Strongly Disagreed; D: Disagreed

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